

The hedonic model of Kant's categorical imperative

Sebti Rabah and Bassem Ben Hamed

Sebtirabah1@gmail.com
bassem.benhamed@enetcom.ufs.tn

Ecole National d'Electronique et de Télécommunication
ENET.COM de Sfax Tunis

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Abstract

To represent an ethics of philosophical origin in computational form, thereby enabling agents to adhere to universal and unconditional ethical rules, we propose modifying the hedonic model by introducing ethical constraints based on rule generalization. This enhancement aims to enrich interactions within a heterogeneous multi-agent environment. We specifically explore integrating Immanuel Kant's ethical principles, particularly the categorical imperative, into a multi-agent hedonic game model. While traditionally centered on agents' personal preferences, this model can be refined by incorporating strict moral imperatives.

The outcome of this approach is a formal representation of ethical principles, providing a framework for ethical decision-making in multi-agent systems.

Keywords: Ethical agent, Hedonic games, Meta-ethics, Categorical imperative.

Introduction

With the development of networks and embedded systems, as well as the emergence of large language models capable of reproducing themselves to create new systems, the notion of singularity becomes increasingly natural as we approach artificial general intelligence. At the same time, the challenge of whether artificial intelligence can comprehend and translate moral consciousness arises, representing a major hurdle for simulating human ethics. This consciousness is rooted in a rich philosophical heritage through which humanity has sought to resolve its moral dilemmas.

With the rise of artificial intelligence, a new challenge emerges exploring ethics and ensuring its respect to safeguard humanity and its values. Consequently, it becomes necessary to adopt ethical artificial agents to ensure that these systems uphold human values. The adoption of certain philosophical theories has been proposed, such as Emmanuel Kant's ethics (1785). In this context, we present a formal representation of Kantian ethics to guide artificial agents in acting according to moral principles.

The main idea is that the system must be capable of evaluating whether actions are morally acceptable according to Kantian ethics. To achieve this, we focus on the first formulation of Kant's categorical imperative. In our work, we determine and apply this first formulation without addressing the relationship between the three formulations.

On the other hand, we can use the "hedonic games" model to analyze how agents balance their personal interests with their moral duties and understand the impact of ethical laws on the formation of alliances and groups. Among the challenges lies the difficulty of precisely defining Kantian moral

laws within a mathematical framework, where the application of the categorical imperative could exclude many available options, making the attainment of a stable division more complex.

However, the "hedonic games" model can be an effective tool for representing Kant's categorical imperative, provided it is modified to include strict ethical constraints. In this case, stability is defined not only by personal preferences but also by the compliance of these preferences with universal moral laws. This model is suitable for a heterogeneous multi-agent environment in terms of ethics and goals, where agents can exchange information and form alliances based on shared interests. It can be applied to real-world scenarios such as coordinated military drones, autonomous vehicles, or intelligent medical robots.

If we succeed in integrating the Kantian ethical element into this model, we will achieve several objectives: first, the mathematical formulation of the representation of the categorical imperative, a major challenge until now; second, the formulation of Kantian theory as an ethical concept interacting with a set of agents; and finally, the realization of agent ethical compliance in a modeled environment representing reality. In this paper, we propose a mathematical model that we call the hedonic model of Kant's categorical imperative. This model serves as a formal tool for modeling ethical aspects in various situations.

Similar Works

In machine ethics research, many ethical theories have been made available in the form of formalized models, such as, depending on the case, the modeling of human values (particularly in the case of virtues), see (Vallée, Bonnet, de Swarte 2018), utilitarianism, see (Horty 2001; Arkoudas, Bringsjord, and Bello 2005), the principle of double effect, see (Bentzen 2016; Govindarajuli and Bringsjord 2017), Pareto permissibility, see (Lindner, Bentzen, and Nebel 2017), and Asimov's laws of robotics, see (Winfield, Blum, and Liu 2014). However, for a long time, Kantian deontic ethics had already been proposed for definition and computational implementation, see (Powers 2006; Abney 2012). Powers (2006) proposed three possible ways to define the first formulation of Kant's categorical imperative: through the logic of duty, through non-monotonic logic, or through belief revision. The first formulation of the categorical imperative being that one must will that the principle motivating your action becomes a universal law. However, Powers does not specify how to define a form of it or how to implement it mathematically, thus leaving the first formulation of the categorical imperative an open question.

Nevertheless, (Bentzen and Lindner 2018) presented an approach centered on the second formula of the categorical imperative and proposed a formulation and computational implementation of Kant's theory according to this second formula. Subsequently, (Singh 2022) attempted to provide a general formulation of the categorical imperative using "dyadic deontic logic."

Finally, (Mougan and Brand 2024) presented a framework for Kantian deontic ethics with measures of justice, reiterating Kant's critique of utilitarianism, which is the dominant model in terms of justice measures for artificial intelligence, arguing that principles of justice should conform to the Kantian framework of deontic ethics.

In line with these previous analyses, others have argued for the inapplicability of Kantian artificial intelligence agents from the perspective of authentic Kantian ethics itself, suggesting an alternative vision based instead on utilitarianism, (Manna and Nath 2021). In this work, we will examine the issue while combining utilitarianism and the principle of the categorical imperative.

The Formulation of the Categorical Imperative

In this work, we do not aim to provide a complete philosophical foundation for the formulation of Kant's categorical imperative, as many philosophical complexities make the mathematical representation of these principles difficult. Moreover, even determining their exact meaning leads to a diversity of opinions. Its practical application also remains a subject of debate in philosophical circles. This is due to the intertwining of Kant's moral doctrine with his cognitive theory presented in his work **Critique of Pure Reason**. It is the mind that produces initial knowledge and establishes moral concepts, which, despite their diversity, all refer back to the principle of the categorical imperative, which has three main formulations.

The first formulation: "Act in such a way that the maxim of your action could become a universal law of nature," meaning one must act according to a principle that can be applied to everyone.

The second formulation: "Humanity is an end in itself, and not a means."

The third formulation: "Act according to principles that could become part of a moral kingdom in accordance with the laws of reason."

The challenge lies in the potential conflict between these formulations, especially the third, which insists that moral rules are the product of a purely rational process, transcending consequences and benefits. Applying these rules in reality raises contradictions that put Kantian moral theory to the test. Thus, in this work, we seek to offer a more coherent interpretation aligned with the original principles, focusing solely on the first principle, namely that ethics must be a primary characteristic of actions that can be generalized without contradictions. We aim to formulate this principle within a model including a set of agents with heterogeneous ethical ontologies, who seek to achieve their goals or avoid negative consequences in a shared environment. This model intertwines with the hedonic game, which seeks to establish the stability of alliances based on agents' preferences.

Hedonic Model of Alliance Formation

The problem of forming collective groups has been systematically addressed within the framework of n-player games, also known as coalition games, where, given a fixed partition of agents (players), the question is whether each agent will remain in their current alliance or group, leave it, or even form a new one (Vallée, Bonnet, de Swarte 2018)?

Traditionally, the study of coalition games has relied on a utilitarian approach, where a characteristic function is assumed a priori, corresponding to the utility or interest attributed to the existence of a coalition, which underpins a number of classical results (Morgenstern, Von Neumann, 1953; Nash, 1950). However, in our study, within the framework of hedonic coalition games, each agent expresses their preferences regarding the coalitions they could potentially join (Dreze and Greenberg, 1980). In this context, decision-making is based not on a quantitative measure such as utility, but on qualitative preferences regarding the type of coalition each agent wishes to belong to.

Definition of a Hedonic Game:

A hedonic game is a tuple $HG = \langle N, (\succ_i)_{a_i \in N} \rangle$ where $N = \{a_1, \dots, a_n\}$ denotes the set of agents and \succ_i represents the preferences of agent a_i , expressed as a total pre-order over $N_i = \{C \in N : a_i \in C\}$.

Problem Related to Hedonic Coalition Games

The main problem is to compute a partition Π of a group N such that this partition best satisfies the preferences of each agent.

In the remainder of this article, we denote by P_N the set of all possible partitions of the agents in N .

If we have a given partition $\Pi \in P_N$, then $C_i(\Pi)$ denotes the coalition to which agent a_i belongs in this partition Π .

Defining the Partition that Maximizes Preference Satisfaction

To describe the partition that achieves the highest level of preference satisfaction for the agents, several solution concepts have been proposed in the scientific literature. These concepts determine the properties that partitions must satisfy to be considered stable, meaning that no agent wishes to change coalitions.

Concept of Stability

A partition is considered stable when no agent wishes to join another coalition or create a new coalition because they are dissatisfied with their current coalition.

Application of the Categorical Imperative to the Hedonic Model

The objective here is to introduce the concept of the categorical imperative into a social and collective framework, such as the hedonic model. How can this ethical principle of unconditional rules (regardless of whether they lead to good or bad consequences) be linked to individual decisions and personal interests, as in the hedonic model? Believing that it suffices requires reformulating the objective of the game, as each individual must seek to achieve the highest degree of desire or personal profit (the agent's needs) while simultaneously determining whether their action could become a universal law that everyone could follow without contradiction.

For example, if players decide to make decisions that benefit the individual but cause long-term harm to the collective, such an action could not constitute a law to which everyone could adhere (which would be contradictory to the collective interest). Thus, an action that achieves personal profit should only be guaranteed by ensuring compliance with the possibility of universalization without contradictions, as required by the first formulation of Kant's categorical imperative.

In this regard, players must each act according to a rule that could pass as a universal law valid in all cases. That is, instead of a player acting solely based on personal profit to be deemed "good," they must ensure that their choice could also be applicable to all other players. In this case, the best strategy would not be one that maximizes only personal profit but also simultaneously adheres to principles of justice, equality, and respect for human dignity—precisely those defined by the categorical imperative.

System Development

The main idea is to build a realistic system based on Kantian ethical ontology, where the hedonic game helps simulate reality through agents seeking to achieve specific goals and satisfy their needs, whether utilitarian or qualitative. Integrating ethical oversight into an open and interconnected system requires general ontological knowledge, with the ability to exchange information between agents about their desires and objectives. Then, it involves arriving at a uniform judgment regarding ethics and the acceptance of behaviors and rules. The Kantian ethical philosophy is considered a meta-ethics, meaning that it does not merely determine rules and actions but defines the characteristics of acceptable ethical actions or rules and can influence the preference order of these rules. Based on this, we will establish an integration between the hedonic game and Kantian meta-

ethics¹, where the first section addresses how to select ethical rules consistent with the principle of the categorical imperative, while the second section deals with aligning decisions with this same Kantian principle.

Figure 1: Internal Model of a Kantian Ethical Agent

I. Conformity of Rules

In this first section, we will examine how the ethical rules of a group of agents can be harmonized to ensure coherence that respects the first formulation of the categorical imperative. In other words, we will explore the possibility of generalization without contradictions.

Phase 1:

Rethinking Goals and Behaviors

Within the framework of traditional hedonic games, agents shape their preferences according to their individual or collective desires. However, this model can be enriched by integrating ethical constraints, creating scenarios where personal interests compete with collective interests or moral norms. This dynamic adds complexity to the game, as choices must be redefined in light of established ethical principles rather than responding solely to utilitarian considerations. Furthermore, preferences can have a qualitative dimension, embodying values such as justice or freedom, and are not limited to utilitarian aspects. This model resonates with Kantian philosophy, where moral commitment is fundamentally independent of consequences but relies on the ability to generalize from the ethical rule. To apply this approach concretely within the game, we establish the following rules:

A. Definition of Agents

Let the set of agents $N = \{a_1, a_2... a_n\}$ represent a group of individuals or entities interacting with each other. Each agent has personal preferences ($>i$), which now incorporate ethical considerations akin to the categorical imperative.

B. Integration of the Categorical Imperative into Preferences

It is possible to modify the preference order ($>i$) to include strict ethical constraints: whenever a particular coalition violates, for example, Kantian moral law (e.g., treating others merely as a means and not as an end), that coalition becomes unacceptable regardless of the level of satisfaction it

¹ As indicated in Figure 1, the meta-ethical model pertains to the revision of ethical rules and preferences, as well as the decisions that ultimately translate into actions.

provides to the agent. For instance, if agent a_i prefers a particular coalition but that coalition violates the moral law "Treat everyone as an end," this excludes the coalition from the agent a_i options.

C. Definition of Ethical Stability

In the context of the Kantian hedonic game, ethical stability is defined as follows: A partition Π is ethically stable if no agent wishes to leave their coalition to join another without violating Kantian moral laws. In other words, even if an agent would be more satisfied by joining a new coalition, that coalition must conform to the categorical imperative. Thus, stabilization is defined not only by personal preferences but also by adherence to universal moral laws, which serve as the foundation for all personal choices.

D. Practical Example

Suppose we have three agents (a_1, a_2, a_3) and three possible coalitions:

Coalition $C_1 = \{a_1, a_2\}$

Coalition $C_2 = \{a_2, a_3\}$

Coalition $C_3 = \{a_1, a_3\}$

Agent a_1 prefers C_1 because it believes it brings significant benefit: $\succ_1 = C_1 \succ_1 C_3$.

Agent a_2 prefers C_2 , then $\succ_2 = C_2 \succ_1 C_1$.

Agent a_3 prefers C_3 , then $\succ_3 = C_3 \succ_1 C_2$.

However, if joining C_2 requires a_2 to exploit a_3 as a means to achieve its own interest, this coalition is excluded because it violates Kantian moral law.

E. Preliminary Results

The hedonic game is a model that captures the interplay between agents' interests and their ethical dimensions. This model illustrates how ethical laws can guide the formation of alliances and groups. However, the challenge is twofold: on the one hand, the rigid framework of Kantian moral laws must be quantified within a mathematical framework; on the other hand, the application of the categorical imperative leads to numerous exclusions, favoring the robustness of choices that allow for the attainment of a stable partition.

Phase 2:

Exploration of Generalizable Rules

In this section, we will examine whether it is possible to adhere to ethical rules that are derived from the personal preferences of agents but converted into general ethical laws. We use the dual aspects of «possibility of generalization» and «impossibility of generalization» to determine whether generalizable ethical rules can be obtained.

Basic Hypothesis

The system will consist of a set of agents $N = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n\}$, each with their personal preferences, which may be quantitative (based on measurable interests, potentially numerical utilities) or qualitative (based on ordered prescriptions for belonging to an alliance, without quantitative measurement).

Definition of an Ethical Rule

An ethical rule is deduced from the personal (or individual) preferences of each agent. For example, if agent a_1 always prefers alliances that respect the rights of others, this could correspond to the ethical rule «respect the rights of others in the alliance».

Test of Generalization Possibility

- Possibility of Generalization: If the ethical rule is coherent and accepted by all agents without conflict, it is a candidate to become a universal law.
- Impossibility of Generalization: If the rule conflicts with the preferences of some agents or leads to incoherent results when generalized, it is not valid as a universal law.

1. Key Elements of the Mathematical Model

A. Set of Agents

Let us assume we have a set of agents $N = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n\}$.

B. Preferences

For each agent $a_i \in N$, there exists an order relation \succ_i that represents their preferences. If the preferences are qualitative (as in the qualitative hedonic model), \succ_i expresses the ranking of alliances based on their ethical quality.

C. Ethical Rules

For each agent a_i , an ethical rule R_i can be extracted from their preferences. The rule R_i represents the rule that agent a_i wishes to apply.

D. Partition

The partition Π is a division of the set of agents N into sub-alliances C_1, C_2, \dots, C_k .

E. Compatibility of Rules

We define a compatibility function $T(R_i, R_j)$ that measures the degree of compatibility between two ethical rules R_i and R_j .

If $T(R_i, R_j) = 1$, the rules are compatible.

If $T(R_i, R_j) = 0$, the rules are incompatible.

2. Classification Rules

A. Universal Rule

An ethical rule R is said to be universal if it can be accepted by all agents in all possible scenarios:

$$R \text{ universal} \Leftrightarrow \forall i \in N, T(R, R_i) = 1$$

B. Impossible Rule

An ethical rule R is said to be impossible if it is rejected by all agents:

$$R \text{ impossible} \Leftrightarrow \forall i \in N, T(R, R_i) = 0$$

C. Conventional Rule

An ethical rule R is said to be conventional within a specific alliance $C \subseteq N$ if it is accepted by all agents in that alliance:

$$R \text{ conventional in } C \Leftrightarrow \forall i \in C, T(R, R_i) = 1$$

3. Mathematical Modeling

A. Representation of Preferences

Suppose each agent a_i has a set of possible ethical rules R_i . The preferences of agent a_i can be represented by a function:

$f_i : R_i \rightarrow [0, 1]$, where:

$f_i(R) = 1$ if the rule R is the most preferred by a_i .

$f_i(R) = 0$ if the rule R is totally unacceptable for a_i .

B. Compatibility Test

To test the compatibility of two ethical rules, we use the function $T(R_i, R_j)$:

$$T(R_i, R_j) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{si } R_i \text{ et } R_j \text{ are compatible} \\ 0 & \text{si } R_i \text{ et } R_j \text{ are incompatible} \end{cases}$$

C. Verification of Universality

To find universal rules, we verify whether the rule R is compatible with all other rules:

$$R \text{ universal} \Leftrightarrow \prod_{i=1}^n T(R, R_i) = 1$$

where \prod denotes the product of all values.

D. Verification of Impossibility

To find impossible rules, we verify whether the rule R is incompatible with all other rules:

$$R \text{ impossible} \Leftrightarrow \sum_{i=1}^n T(R, R_i) = 0$$

where \sum denotes the sum of all values.

Verification of Conventional Rules

To find conventional rules within an alliance $C \subseteq N$, we verify whether the rule R is compatible with all rules in C :

$$R \text{ conventional in } C \Leftrightarrow \prod_{i \in C} T(R, R_i) = 1$$

4. Practical Example

Agents:

$N = \{a_1, a_2, a_3\}$.

Preferences:

a_1 : Prefers the rule R_1 ="Respect the rights of others".

a_2 : Prefers the rule R_2 ="Achieve the common interest".

a_3 : Rejects the rule R_3 ="Exploitation".

Compatibility:

$T(R_1, R_2) = 1$: The rules R_1 and R_2 are compatible.

$T(R_1, R_3) = 0$: The rules R_1 and R_3 are incompatible.

$T(R_2, R_3) = 0$: The rules R_2 and R_3 are incompatible.

Results:

1. The rule R_1 "Respect the rights of others" could be universal if it is accepted by all agents.
2. The rule R_3 "Exploitation" is impossible because it is rejected by all agents.
3. If a_1 and a_2 form an alliance, the rule R_1 or R_2 could be conventional within that alliance.

II. Conformity of Actions

In this second section, we will detail how actions resulting from decisions aligned with the various ethical frameworks of agents can achieve coherence with the first formulation of the categorical imperative.

Phase 1:

Rethinking Behavioral Criteria

In the hedonic game, each individual typically seeks to maximize their personal satisfaction. However, in this context, the individual must also subject their pursuit of pleasure to the condition that their action could be universally applied without contradiction. If players choose to maximize their personal happiness but cause long-term collective harm, such an action cannot become a universal law that everyone can respect. Two key rules must be respected:

- Players must agree to use a rule that could and should become a universal law, meaning it must be applicable in all situations. In other words, it is not enough for a player to maximize their own advantage; they must ensure that their choice can serve as an example for everyone.
- The "best strategy" is one that aligns both with the logic of self-satisfaction and with the first formulation of the categorical imperative (the possibility of generalization).

1.Key Elements of the Model

A. Players

Each agent has a personal interest (achieving happiness or benefit).

B. Decisions

Every decision made by a player must be universally generalizable, meaning that every agent can perform the same action without contradiction or harm.

C. System

- A reward system can be established in the game, where points are awarded based on actions that respect the categorical imperative.
- The consequences of decisions are linked to their evaluation: whether they support only personal interest or align with the categorical imperative.

D. Example Application

Consider a cooperative game among players. In this game, happiness points are awarded to each player based on their decisions. However, there is a condition: every decision made must be universally applicable:

- If a player steals from another to gain an extra happiness point, they may achieve short-term personal benefit. However, this strategy cannot become a universal law without leading to chaos.
- If a player decides to cooperate with others to achieve mutually beneficial outcomes, such as sharing resources or helping others, this strategy can be generalized and imitated by everyone.

E. Basic Concepts

Player Happiness (Si): Represents the satisfaction or benefit of player i.

Player Decision (di):** Represents the action chosen by player i.

Ethical Rule of the Decision I(di): A function evaluating whether the decision d_i conforms to ethical rules.

$I(d_i)=1$: If the decision conforms to ethical values (categorical imperative).and $I(d_i)=0$: If the decision does not conform.

Personal Benefit f(di):This function calculates the happiness that the player gains from their personal decision d_i .

Social Value (Collective Benefit (G)): Represents the benefit that the group obtains when a set of decisions respects the categorical imperative.

Objective: Each player seeks to maximize their personal happiness S_i , but they must also consider the categorical imperative. Therefore, they must choose decisions that can be generalized, meaning that all players can make the same choice without ethical contradiction.

2. Formal Representation of the Model

1. Individual Happiness Equation

Let us begin by determining a calculation method for the individual happiness S_i of player i . If their decision d_i aligns with the categorical imperative (i.e., $I(d_i)=1$), the player's happiness will simply be a function of their decision: $S_i=f(d_i)$. However, if their decision contradicts the categorical imperative (i.e., $I(d_i)=0$), happiness diminishes since the decision goes against ethical principles.

$$S_i = f(d_i) \times I(d_i)$$

2. Collective Benefit Function

To achieve collective happiness (social benefit) as the sum of individual happiness, with ethical values being respected, the total happiness of all players is considered, and decisions are measured against the categorical imperative.

$$G = \sum_{i=1}^n S_i = \sum_{i=1}^n f(d_i) \times I(d_i)$$

This ensures that only ethical decisions contribute positively to the collective benefit.

3. Game Equilibrium

In the game, equilibrium is reached when no player can improve their individual position by changing their decision while maintaining compliance with the categorical imperative. We use the principle of the dominant strategy, which represents the best decision for a player given the decisions of other players.

If for a player i , their decision d_i is the best for them in terms of personal benefit, and this decision respects the categorical imperative, we call this a dominant strategy. Equilibrium occurs when:

$$\forall i, d_i^* = \arg \max_{d_i} (f(d_i) \times I(d_i) + \sum_{j \neq i} f(d_j) \times I(d_j))$$

In other words, the individual happiness of the player must be optimal when they take into account all possible ethical decisions of others.

4. Integration of the Categorical Imperative

To apply the categorical imperative in the context of the hedonic game, we must ensure that all decisions made are generalizable without contradiction or harm. We use the following condition:

$$\forall i, \forall j : I(d_i) = 1 \Rightarrow I(d_j) = 1$$

Thus, if the decision of player i align with ethical values (categorical imperative), the decisions of all other players must also align with the same values. This ensures that ethical values are consistent across the actions of all agents.

5. Practical Example

Consider an example with three players in the game (A, B, C), where each player must make a decision (strategy):

- If player A chooses decision d_1 , which aligns with the categorical imperative, their happiness will be:

$$S_A = f(d_1) \times I(d_1)$$

- If player B chooses decision d_2 , which does not align with the categorical imperative, their happiness will be:

$$S_B = f(d_2) \times I(d_2) = f(d_2) \times 0$$

- If player C chooses decision d_3 , which aligns with the categorical imperative, their happiness will be:

$$S_C = f(d_3) \times I(d_3)$$

Calculation of Collective Happiness

The social benefit will be the sum of individual happiness:

$$G = S_A + S_B + S_C = f(d_1) \times 1 + f(d_2) \times 0 + f(d_3) \times 1$$

Equilibrium Analysis

The game is in a state of (soft equilibrium) when no player can improve their happiness without changing the decisions of others. Each player must choose their strategy based on the analysis of the ethical decisions of other players.

6. Dominant Strategy and Collective Equilibrium

We evaluate the dominant strategy, which is the one that maximizes the player's personal gain while complying with the categorical imperative. If d_i^* is the optimal strategy for player i , then the following equation must be satisfied:

$$\forall i, d_i^* = \arg \max_{d_i} (f(d_i) \times I(d_i) + \sum_{j \neq i} f(d_j) \times I(d_j))$$

Player i will choose their strategy d_i^* to maximize their benefit while considering the impact of the decisions of others. Taking into account the collective equilibrium, decisions are made such that the moral decision is optimal for all players. Collective equilibrium means that all players have chosen strategies that comply with the categorical imperative, which implies:

$$\forall i, d_i^* = \arg \max_{d_i} (f(d_i) \times I(d_i))$$

Thus, each player makes the decision that maximizes their benefit in accordance with ethical principles.

7. Integration of Social Consequences with Individual Happiness

Assuming that players are not independent of one another and may influence each other, we could include social consequences in individual happiness through an aggregated function that accounts for reciprocal interactions between players.

Sum of Happiness with Reciprocal Effects

While each player chooses their decision based on their own happiness, they also consider the impact of others in their calculations. For example, if player i decides to make an immoral decision (such as d_i not complying with the categorical imperative), it affects their own happiness as well as that of others. The equation can be formulated as follows:

$$S_i = f(d_i) \times I(d_i) + \sum_{j \neq i} \delta_{ij} \times f(d_j) \times C(d_j)$$

Where δ_{ij} is a coefficient that determines how the decision of player j influences the happiness of player i . If all decisions align with ethics, these effects are positive. The collective benefit with reciprocal effects, or social value, accounting for the interactions between players, will be:

$$G = \sum_{i=1}^n (f(d_i) \times I(d_i) + \sum_{j \neq i} \delta_{ij} \times f(d_j) \times I(d_j))$$

III. Summary and Applications

After formulating these mathematical equations incorporating Kant's categorical imperative into the hedonic game, these equations allow us to simulate how agents select their individual decisions in accordance with universal ethical principles. To achieve this, it is necessary to consistently define the following characteristics:

1. Define the utility function $f(d_i)$ for each player based on the game's characteristics.
2. Define the ethical evaluation $I(d_i)$ that determines whether decisions comply with the categorical imperative.
3. Calculate the collective happiness G , which accounts for the social effects of individual decisions.
4. Determine dominant strategies and game equilibrium while considering ethical principles.

A. Basic Steps

We will now proceed to set up the mathematical simulation model of the hedonic game using the following equations, incorporating Kant's categorical imperative. This model aims to replicate decision-making in a game where individual utility is combined with the categorical imperative and the consideration of how others' choices affect collective happiness.

To implement this model, we will follow these basic steps:

1. **Define the game's characteristics:** Specify the number of players, their available strategies, and the happiness function for each player.
2. **Define the parameters: Determine the utility** function for each player and establish the ethical principles (in this case, the categorical imperative).
3. **Simulate decisions:** Each player chooses their decision based on the utility they gain, provided it complies with ethical principles.
4. **Calculate collective happiness and equilibrium:** Compute individual and collective happiness after decisions are made, and then identify the collective equilibrium.

B. Simulation Model

1. **Number of players and their strategies:** Suppose we have 3 players (A, B, C) in the game. Each player can choose one of 2 strategies (either a moral decision or an immoral decision). The utility function for each player is $f(d_i) = 10 - d_i^2$, where d_i is the number chosen by the player from the set $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$. If the player chooses a morally compliant decision, then $I(d_i) = 1$, and $I(d_i) = 0$ if the decision is not morally compliant.

2. **Define decisions:** Each player makes their decisions based on the available options. However, if a decision is immoral, it significantly affects their happiness.
3. **Dominant strategies and equilibrium:** The goal is to find the optimal strategies for each player to maximize their individual utility while adhering to the categorical imperative.
4. **Mutual effects between players:** The social impact of each player's decisions must be considered. If a player makes an immoral decision, it may negatively affect others.

C. Numerical Simulation

Now, we can write a code to simulate this hedonic game with Kant's categorical imperative. The code will include:

- Calculation of individual happiness based on the decision.
- Calculation of collective happiness, accounting for the impact of other players' decisions.
- Calculation of the game's equilibrium.

Python Code for Simulation:

```
import random

# Number of players
num_players = 3

# Utility function for each player (depends on the decision d_i)
def utility(d_i):
    return 10 - d_i**2

# Function for compliance with the categorical imperative (moral values)
def ethical_compliance(d_i):
    # Here, we can define moral values such that if the decision >= 3, it is morally compliant
    return 1 if d_i >= 3 else 0

# Function to calculate the individual happiness of a player
def individual_happiness(d_i):
    return utility(d_i) * ethical_compliance(d_i)

# Function to calculate collective happiness (sum of individual happiness)
def collective_happiness(actions):
    total_happiness = 0
    for a_i in actions:
        total_happiness += individual_happiness(d_i)
    return total_happiness

# Game simulation
def simulate_game():
    # Each player chooses a random decision from {1, 2, 3, 4, 5}
    actions = [random.choice([1, 2, 3, 4, 5]) for _ in range(num_players)]
    print(f"Player decisions: {actions}")

    # Calculate collective happiness
    total_happiness = collective_happiness(actions)
    print(f"Collective happiness: {total_happiness}")
```

```
# Find the equilibrium (each player chooses the decision that maximizes their happiness while
being moral)
best_actions = []
for i in range(num_players):
    best_action = max([1, 2, 3, 4, 5], key=lambda d: individual_happiness(d))
    best_actions.append(best_action)

print(f"Optimal decisions in equilibrium: {best_actions}")
return actions, total_happiness, best_actions

# Run the simulation
simulate_game()
```

Code Explanation

- **Utility Function (utility):** Determines the utility each player gains based on their decision. Here, we use a simple function $f(d_i)=10 - d_i^2$, where utility decreases as the decision value increases.
- **Moral Compliance Function (ethical_compliance):** Determines whether a decision complies with ethical principles. In this example, if the strategy is greater than or equal to 3, the decision complies with the categorical imperative.
- **Individual Happiness Function (individual_happiness):** Calculates the happiness of each player based on their decision, taking into account moral compliance.
- **Collective Happiness Function (collective_happiness):** Calculates the collective happiness by summing the individual happiness of all players.
- **Game Simulation (simulate_game):** Simulates the game by allowing each player to choose a random decision from {1, 2, 3, 4, 5}, then calculates the collective happiness. Finally, the program identifies the best decision for each player to maximize utility while considering moral compliance.

Simulation Execution

When the code is executed, the program generates random decisions for each player, and then calculates the collective happiness based on these decisions. It then determines the optimal decisions in the case of equilibrium, where compliance with the categorical imperative is taken into account. Expected results include:

- Random decisions made by each player (the chosen strategies).
- The resulting collective happiness from these decisions.
- The optimal decisions in equilibrium, where each player chooses the strategy that maximizes their utility while adhering to the categorical imperative.

Modifications and Improvements

To enhance the utility function, it could be refined to incorporate more types of moral decisions and develop more efficient algorithms to detect dominant strategies. Some areas to explore include:

- Adding different levels of moral values (categorical imperative).
- Increasing the complexity of the utility function to include other factors influencing player happiness.
- Representing deeper interactions between players, such as decisions indirectly or long-term affecting others.
- Using search algorithms to more efficiently discover dominant strategies in game equilibrium.
- Analyzing game dynamics using time-based simulations to observe how player strategies evolve over time (dynamic system).

Improvement 1: Adding Different Levels of Moral Values

Currently, we consider total compliance or non-compliance with ethics (1 or 0). However, we can increase the number of compliance levels, allowing decisions to be partially ethical. For example:

- $I(d_i) = 1$ if the decision is perfectly ethical.
- $I(d_i) = 0.5$ if the decision is imperfect but acceptable.
- $I(d_i) = 0$ if the decision is completely incompatible with ethics.
- We can enhance the moral compliance function to take multiple value:

```
# Moral compliance function (multiple levels)
def ethical_compliance(d_i):
    # Levels of compliance with the categorical imperative:
    if d_i >= 4:
        return 1 # Full compliance with ethics
    elif d_i == 3:
        return 0.5 # Partial compliance
    else:
        return 0 # No compliance with ethics
```

Improvement 2: Increase the Complexity of the Utility Function

Now, suppose players must make decisions not only based on their individual choices but also on the collective strategy. We can then add a symbolic variable to account for the collective effect of choices.

```
# Utility function with collective effects
def utility(d_i, group_actions):
    # Impact of collective decisions
    group_impact = sum([d_j for d_j in group_actions]) / len(group_actions)
    return 10 - d_i**2 + 0.5 * group_impact
```

Here, we have added a simple effect of collective decisions, so that the sum of the decisions of other players affects the happiness of the player. This function can be modified to make the impact larger or smaller.

Improvement 3: Representing Player Interaction

We can also increase the complexity of the interaction between players by creating a network of interactions where each player is affected by the sum of the decisions of the other players. The simulation model can be adjusted to account for the mutual impact of decisions among players.

```
# Mutual effect between players
def collective_happiness(actions):
    total_happiness = 0
    for i in range(len(actions)):
        # Impact of other players' decisions
        group_influence = sum(actions[j] for j in range(len(actions)) if j != i)
        total_happiness += individual_happiness(actions[i]) + 0.3 * group_influence
    return total_happiness
```

Improvement 4: Searching for Dominant Strategies Using Search Algorithms

To optimize the search for dominant strategies, we could use search methods such as dynamic programming, genetic algorithms, Nash equilibrium search, or optimization techniques to determine the optimal choice in the game (i.e., dominant strategies present in a game equilibrium). This supports our reasoning, as we can find the dominant strategy more quickly, especially in the case of a more complex game with a large number of players and possible decisions.

Here is a basic method for using dynamic programming to search for a dominant strategy:

```
# Algorithm for finding the optimal strategy
def find_dominant_strategy(num_players):
    # Using a dynamic programming or optimization search algorithm
    strategies = [1, 2, 3, 4, 5] # Possible strategies for each player
    best_strategies = []
    for i in range(num_players):
        # Find the strategy that maximizes the player's satisfaction
        best_strategy = max(strategies, key=lambda d: individual_happiness(d))
        best_strategies.append(best_strategy)
    return best_strategies
```

Improvement 5: Dynamic Time Simulation (Game Evolution)

If we want to analyze the dynamics of the game over time, we can simulate the evolution of decisions over time. For example, each player can update their strategy based on the results they observe from others.

```
# Simulation of game evolution over time
def dynamic_simulation(steps=10):
    actions = [random.choice([1, 2, 3, 4, 5]) for _ in range(num_players)]
    for step in range(steps):
        print(f"Step {step + 1} - Player decisions: {actions}")
        total_happiness = collective_happiness(actions)
        print(f"Collective happiness: {total_happiness}")
        # Updating player strategies based on interactions
        for i in range(num_players):
            new_action = max([1, 2, 3, 4, 5], key=lambda d: individual_happiness(d))
            actions[i] = new_action
    # Run the dynamic simulation of evolution
    dynamic_simulation()
```

Possible Future Improvements

The presented model supports avenues for improvement by incorporating potential means to enhance certain aspects. Among these, one could consider, for example, using genetic algorithms to generate new strategies and improve them over generations. Additionally, it could be envisioned to simulate the game in broader environments with a larger range of players, which would introduce greater complexity to the game, thereby enabling a better analysis of collective behaviors. Finally, the introduction of a machine learning model that allows players to refine their decisions over time, using data from past experiences, would make the model more dynamic and scalable.

By introducing long-term dynamics (e.g., the impact of decisions on future generations of players), it would then become possible to study how player strategies evolve over time. This might require the adoption of techniques such as complex systems analysis or evolutionary systems modeling.

Conclusion

Our task in this work was twofold: on the one hand, we sought to simplify a complex philosophical rule and transform it into a practical and actionable concept; on the other hand, we worked to make this interpretation mathematically modelable. This was achieved through our interpretation of the categorical imperative principle, where we proposed mathematical formulations enabling the ethical agent to use a meta-ethical judgment mechanism to evaluate the rules and ethical behaviors followed by themselves or other agents in a heterogeneous multi-agent environment. We began by using the hedonic game model, ultimately integrating ethical conditions in the form of the categorical imperative.

References

- [Abney 2012] Abney, K. 2012. Robotics, ethical theory, and metaethics: A guide for the perplexed. In Lina, P.; Abney, K.; and Bekey, G. A., eds., *Robot Ethics: The Ethical and Social Implications of Robotics*. MIT Press. 35–52.
- [Arkoudas, Bringsjord, and Bello 2005] Arkoudas, K.; Bringsjord, S.; and Bello, P. 2005. Toward ethical robots via mechanized deontic logic. Technical report, AAAI Fall Symposium on Machine Ethics, AAAI.
- [Bentzen 2016] Bentzen, M. 2016. The principle of double effect applied to ethical dilemmas of social robots. In *Robophilosophy 2016/TRANSOR 2016: What Social Robots Can and Should Do*. IOS Press. 268–279.
- [Dreze, Greenberg, 1980] Dreze J. H., Greenberg J. 1980. Hedonic coalitions: Optimality and stability. *Econometrica*, vol. 48, no 4, p. 987–1003.
- [Govindarajuli and Bringsjord 2017] Govindarajuli, N. S., and Bringsjord, S. 2017. On automating the doctrine of double effect. In *Proceedings of the Twenty-Sixth International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence (IJCAI)*. 4722–4730.
- [Horty 2001] Horty, J. F. 2001. *Agency and Deontic Logic*. Oxford University Press.
- [Lindner and Bentzen 2018] Lindner, F., and Bentzen, M. 2018. A Formalization of Kant’s Second Formulation of the Categorical Imperative.
- [Lindner, Bentzen, and Nebel 2017] Lindner, F.; Bentzen, M.; and Nebel, B. 2017. The HERA approach to morally competent robots. In *Proceedings of the 2017 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*. IEEE/RSJ.
- [Manna and Nath 2021] Manna, R., and Nath, R. 2021. *Kantian Moral Agency and the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence*
- [Morgenstern, Von Neumann, 1953] Morgenstern O., Von Neumann J. 1953. *Theory of games and economic behavior*. Princeton University Press.
- [Mougan et Brand 2024] Mougan, C., and Brand, J. 2024. *Kantian Deontology Meets AI Alignment: Towards Morally Grounded Fairness Metrics*
- [Nash, 1950] Nash J. F. 1950. Equilibrium points in n-person games. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, vol. 36, no 1, p. 48–49.
- [Powers 2006] Powers, T. M. 2006. Prospects for a kantian machine. *IEEE Intelligent Systems* 21(4):46–51.
- [Sebti, Ben Hamed, 2025] Sebti R., Ben Hamed B. 2025. Intégration de l’éthique de Kant pour le jugement des systèmes multi-agents.
- [Singh 2022] Singh, L. 2022. *Automated Kantian Ethics: A Faithful Implementation*
- [Vallée, Bonnet, de Swarte 2018] Vallée, T.; Bonnet, G., and de Swarte, T. 2018. Modélisation de valeurs humaines : le cas des vertus dans les jeux hédoniques. *Revue d’intelligence artificielle – no 4/2018*, 519–546
- [Winfield, Blum, and Liu 2014] Winfield, A. F.; Blum, C.; and Liu, W. 2014. Towards an ethical robot: internal models, consequences and ethical action selection. In Mistry, M.; Leonardis, A.; M. Witkowski; and Melhuish, C., eds., *Advances in Autonomous Robotics Systems*. Springer. 85–96